

Pilot Evaluation 2: Developing a concept for a Una Europa collaboration platform

Final Version

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Summary

The aim of this pilot was to develop a concept for an Una Europa collaboration platform. The platform was envisioned to consist of an evolving set of tools and services for cross-disciplinary and cross-sectoral collaboration and networking within the Una Europa ecosystem and throughout the R&I lifecycle on the prioritised global challenges. Initially, a number of signature projects were planned to be selected for testing the tools, activities, and consolidated support services.

The approach to develop the pilot was comprehensive and linked to all seven transformation modules, with the following modules being the main focus of the pilot: (2) strengthen human capital; (3) sharing infrastructure and resources; (4) engage non-academic actors; and (7) explore joint university structures.

The development of the pilot was achieved by a number of actions that can be separated into two categories:

- A series of consultations and workshops: The potential needs and requirements of a collaboration platform were first identified and discussed in regular Una Europa RCC meetings and in two dedicated workshop sessions, one with the One Health steering committee and one with the public-, private-, and 3rd sector collaboration cluster (PPTSC). Further input was gained via a questionnaire circulated among all the Una.Resin WPs and clusters. From this questionnaire, the main desires and needs of a collaborative platform could be distilled.
- Mapping procedures: A preliminary mapping of existing research portals at the 11 partner institutions was conducted. This preliminary activity laid the groundwork of a potential and substantial follow-up mapping of commercial platforms, as identified in the consultations and workshops. Pre-existing platforms could either be used as best practice examples from which to base an Una Europa platform, or in their existing form.

The key project **outcome** was the identification, in consultation with the Una Europa community, of the needs and desirable functionalities of a collaborative platform and, in turn, the aspects that should be addressed by the platform and areas in which the platform should foster collaboration. These can be summarised as follows:

- Developing careers and skills.
- Research Funding Portals.
- Research Portals (Research Information System).
- Sharing information on RIRs.
- Enhancing citizen science in research.

The most important insight gained from stakeholder consultations was that the platform should be simple, intuitive, and easy to use. All given information would need to be visible and as transparent as possible. For this to be an efficient tool for researchers and external partners, it should facilitate their work and not add more complexity to their daily tasks. The target users

of the platform are not homogenous, and the functions needed are dependent on the user. The two key users will be academic researchers and research professionals. Under the first group, the early and advanced career stage researchers may need different support and, thus, also different tools. On the other hand, the research professionals need tools to support the researchers, but also tools to advance their own career and distil best practices, which will benefit both the individual professionals and their institutions.

During the project lifecycle, Una.Futura was launched as the second phase of funding for Una Europa under the umbrella of Erasmus+. As part of Una.Futura, Una Europa vzw was tasked to design and develop a comprehensive platform, “Una.Connect”. Una.Resin is working closely with Una Europa vzw to make sure that the **lessons learnt** and insights from this project are used in the process of conceptualising a broader Una Europa platform, with WP1 members participating in the stakeholder consultations for the design of the platform. The main findings and preliminary results of this pilot have been communicated to the Una Europa vzw and this report will be used in the further conceptualisation of the Una.Connect platform. This phase will start in 2024 and the final product will be live by the end of the Una Futura project in 2026.

To address urgent research-related needs in the short term, prior to the establishment of a comprehensive platform, Una Europa should leverage commercially available products and further develop its website. These urgent needs include information on research funding calls, tools to facilitate Eols and subsequent matchmaking, and listing our partner institutions' research portals to aid in identifying potential collaborators. Additionally, tools are needed to share online training courses for researchers and research professionals that are offered by our partner institutions or which have been jointly developed. Coordination of these efforts will be the responsibility of Una Europa vzw, with research professionals taking on advisory roles. In the medium term, a tool for sharing information on research and data infrastructures will be required. In the long term, Una Europa should aim to explore the possibilities of developing AI-based tools that can collect data from our partner universities' research portals, enabling seamless matchmaking between researchers, research groups, and interdisciplinary units. Some of our partner universities are currently developing similar approaches that could serve as pilots and support with identifying best practice.

Objectives and aims of the pilot project

Una.Resin WP1 was first tasked to pilot methods to accelerate cross-disciplinary and cross-sectoral collaboration and networking with the aim of addressing the priority global challenges, with this pilot action focused on developing a concept for an Una Europa collaboration platform. The platform was envisioned to consist of an evolving set of tools and services for cross-disciplinary and cross-sectoral collaboration and networking within the Una Europa ecosystem and throughout the R&I lifecycle, with a specific focus on fostering collaboration and networking that was responsive to the priority global challenges. The main ideas for a joint collaborative platform included these tasks:

- Increase the visibility and fields of expertise of the Una Europa researchers;
- Allow for matchmaking and collaboration to create high-quality consortia for acquiring competitive funding;
- Allow for matchmaking for early-career researcher for joint projects;
- Allow for joint international doctoral training modules to be stored and processed;

- Allow the search for specific profiles and keywords, and the posting of calls of interest, in particular in the interest of early-career researchers; and
- Allow for collaboration beyond the sphere of academia, e.g., in citizen science projects.

The primary aim for the pilot was to establish a digitally enhanced one-stop-shop or efficient combination of modules for fostering research collaboration within the Alliance. This resource could offer support in identifying relevant funding opportunities, advancing research initiatives, and facilitating innovation within the shared Una Europa ecosystem. The overall aim of Una.Resin has been to lay the groundwork for the development of the common Una Europa R&I ecosystem. As a part of this, this pilot has sought to develop a collaborative tool for advancing cooperation in R&I within the universities and beyond the sphere of academia.

The approach to develop the pilot was comprehensive and linked to all seven transformation modules but acutely addressed the following modules: (2) strengthen human capital; (3) share research infrastructures; (4) engage non-academic actors; and (7) explore joint university structures.

Initial design and implementation of the pilot project Consultations and Workshops

The potential needs and requirements of a collaboration platform were discussed in regular meetings and in two dedicated workshop sessions, namely:

- Workshops in connection to RCC meetings: 13/12/2021 (online), 14/02/2022 (online), 17/03/2022 in Paris, 02/06/2022 in Helsinki, 29/11/2022 in Edinburgh, 08/06/2023 in Leiden.
- Workshop with the One Health Focus area self-steering committee in Bertinoro in February 2022.
- PPTSC workshop at the Freie Universität Berlin, 04-06/04/2022.
- Strategic discussions with the chairs of the Una Europa self-steering committee in February 2023.
- Pilot Evaluation 1: Una Europa R&I strategy workshop and the Horizon Europe Pillar II matchmaking process.

The Una Europa RCC, in close collaboration with WP1, played a major role supporting the development of the internal processes and sharing best practices from their home institutions. The RCC members helped to identify the processes and the potential user groups. Their input was of great value with regards to the technical and administrative feasibility of the whole pilot. They also served as contact points for engaging academics, as well as research funding professionals. The One Health self-steering committee was a main point of contact for this pilot.

Further input was gained via a questionnaire circulated among all the Una.Resin WPs and clusters. The following key questions were posed:

- Based on the Una.Resin outcomes, what communication needs did you identify? What support for matchmaking is needed?
- What are the main tasks an Una Europa communication platform would need to fulfil from your WP/Cluster's perspective?
- What are the main support needs for communication and matchmaking from the Una

Europa vzw?

From this questionnaire, the main desires and needs of a collaborative platform could be distilled.

Mapping

In the consultations with the academic community, they stressed the need to have access to information about the research areas and experiences of other Una Europa colleagues. A mapping exercise of existing research portals at the 11 partner institutions was carried out that, as a first step, could be shared on the Una Europa joint platform/homepage. At a later stage, this could serve as the basis for a joint portal that researchers could use to connect with suitable colleagues for matchmaking purposes or joint applications.

The pilot also aimed to map commercial platforms that could fit the needs expressed below. During the project lifecycle, Una Futura was launched as the second phase of funding for Una Europa under the umbrella of Erasmus+. As part of Una.Futura, Una Europa vzw was tasked to design and develop a comprehensive platform, "Una.Connect". Existing commercial platforms should be further explored during the conceptualisation Una.Connect as examples of best practices or simply for use in their existing form.

Challenges and solutions

Shortly after the initiation of the project it was apparent that a universal platform, which incorporates a whole range of tools, would need to be developed and implemented. The design and implementation, understood as two separate tasks to be performed in the lifetime of one pilot, soon proved to be unfeasible from the viewpoint of human and financial resources. It was assumed that there would already be active research collaboration wherein the platform could be piloted during the lifetime of Una.Resin, however this assumption turned out to be incorrect. Thus, it was decided that the limited resources dedicated to the pilot would be focused on understanding the needs and expectations of a collaborative platform and drafting a concept for such a platform.

Outcomes and impact of the pilot project

The key findings regarding the desired functionalities for such a platform are listed below.

Research funding portal

Target group: Academics and research funding professionals

Aims: Sharing information about research funding opportunities and matchmaking for calls

Features needed:

- Joint pool of funding opportunities.
- European funding opportunities.
- National and regional funding opportunities.
- Institutional funding opportunities.
- Platform for researchers' matchmaking for joint applications.
- Collection of interest of researchers at the EoI phase.
- Creation of a repository of relevant information about funding opportunities on a national and European level (e.g., documents, training sessions on how to apply, taking the Horizon call preparatory sessions as an example, etc.).

- Facilitation of interaction between participants (e.g., via a chat functionality).

Who should maintain/operate:

- A commercial platform could be used.
- Research professionals, identified by RCC members, at each university.
- Senior External Funding Advisor at vzw.
- IT-professional(s) at vzw or partner universities.

Strategic goals addressed:

- Supporting Bottom-Up Initiatives.
- Promoting Mobility and Community Building.
- Training Researchers of the Future.
- Digitalising Collaboration.
- Establishing Interdisciplinary Hubs.

Existing commercial products: To be mapped.

Short, middle and long-term goals:

A number of development stages would be required to satisfy all the expressed desired functionalities, although easy workarounds could be used on a short-term perspective that could be then scaled for some functionalities. It is important to note that the tools do not necessarily have to be on the same platform for them to work. At least in the initial stage of this process, Una Europa could use adaptable platforms, like B2B (for more see below). The functions need to be user-friendly and easily found. A feasible process could start with implementing tools that address only specific tasks in the beginning that can then be combined with other functionalities at a later date and if technically possible. This would allow for the process to start rather than waiting until a highly complex digital architecture, which encompasses all desired functionalities, is developed.

A first step, for example, could be to establish a tool for research funding matchmaking, collection of Eols, systematic announcements of international calls, major national and regional funding formats, and institutional funding opportunities. In a long-term perspective, scientists could use the envisaged platform to start discussing collaborations and elaborate on projects. An overview of the research conducted within the funding and organisational framework of Una Europa, as well as the researchers conducting this research, would provide a good opportunity to showcase the thematic Focus Areas within the respective partner institutions, within Una Europa, and beyond academia. Thus, a platform of this kind could also give ample visibility to the Alliance and enable Una Europa to better serve society as a whole, especially by facilitating industrial contacts. External partners would also be able to scout projects that are of interest to them, contact scientists and start matchmaking autonomously.

Developing careers and skills

Target group: Academics and higher education staff

Aims:

- Sharing academic and professional positions available at the partner institutions.
- Training on transversal skills (e.g., interdisciplinary research, open research and research data management, particularities of the academic funding landscape and careers at the partner universities/countries).

Features needed:

- Ability to share and store webinar videos and/or presentations.

- Ability to register for workshop participants.

Who should maintain/operate:

- Ideally the Una Europa vzw would maintain the platform and the features could potentially be added to the Una.Connect platform.
- Research professionals at each university would produce the content as part of the ongoing initiatives/projects. If other professionals would be needed, they could be identified by RCC or other cluster members.
- IT-support professional(s).

Strategic goals addressed:

- Strengthening Collaboration Beyond Academia.
- Supporting Bottom-Up Initiatives.
- Promoting Mobility and Community Building.
- Digitalising Collaboration.

Existing commercial products: To be mapped.

Short, middle and long-term goals:

In the short term, a list with links to the job announcement platforms of individual universities could suffice. For skills training, a page with announcements of future events is a short-term goal. In the middle to long-term perspective, job announcements could be harvested from individual universities' portals and placed on the Una Europa platform to provide an enhanced overview. Regarding the skills training, storing of webinar recordings would be short term goal, with a function to register for announced webinars being a longer-term goal.

Research Portal (Research Information System)

Target group: Academics and higher education staff.

Aims:

- Sharing information on researcher's profiles, publications, patents as well as research results.
- Facilitate matchmaking between researchers for potential cooperation.

Features needed:

- Interoperability of existing research portals of individual universities.
- Harvest data from existing portals.
- Key words search and other search filters (e.g., disciplines).

Who should maintain/operate:

- IT-professionals appointed to coordinate and build the system supported by IT staff at each university, if needed. Academics should not have to manually update data, rather data should be automatically updated

Strategic goals addressed:

- Establishing Interdisciplinary Hubs.
- Training Researchers of the Future.
- Strengthening Collaboration Beyond Academia.
- Supporting Bottom-Up Initiatives.
- Promoting Mobility and Community Building.
- Digitalising Collaboration.
- Promoting openness of RIs and data infrastructures to foster research collaboration.
- Strengthening Research and Data Infrastructure Skills.

- Developing a stronger and more integrated Una Europa Research Infrastructure Ecosystem.

Existing research portals at Una Europa Partner universities:

- UEDIN: [University of Edinburgh Research Explorer](#)
- UH: [University of Helsinki Research Portal](#)
- UNIBO: [Directories](#)
- UP1: [Pages Personnelles Enseignants Chercheurs](#) and [Expert Finder System](#) (beta version)
- JU: [Staff search engine](#)
- KU Leuven: a [research portal](#) with funded projects and information on research infrastructures; a [Publication repository](#) (LIRIAS) with all publication output of KU Leuven researchers; an [institutional research data repository](#) (RDR) for the publication of research data; [KU Leuven Who-is-who](#)
- FUB: no RIS in place yet, considerations to use VIVO; [research data base with research projects](#), [FUB's academic Departments and Central Institutes](#)
- UCM: [Portal de la Investigation](#)
- UCD: [Research Portal](#)
- UZ: no RIS in place yet.
- UL: [Universiteit Leiden's Academic Staff](#)

Existing commercial products: SciVal, SciVal Experts, Pure, Research in View, Converis, Symplectic Elements, VIVO.

Short, middle and long-term goals:

At the beginning, links to the research portals (research information systems) of individual universities could be listed on the platform (Una.Connect or Una Europa Web Pages). Research information systems are already in place in most of the Una Europa universities. For the universities that still do not have such a portal, this could be a good opportunity to both align their needs with the process of developing a platform early on and as an additional resource to create the best possible environment for their academic community. At a later stage, Una Europa could develop ways to harvest data from the individual research information systems, incorporate it in its platform, and ensure its synchronisation and interoperability. The Una Europa platform's data set could commence by harvesting the profiles of researchers and then expand to include publications, patents, and research results. Initial discussion on the possibility to create such functionality started with KU Leuven and University of Edinburgh, where such functions have been developed in-house.

Sharing information on RIRs

Target group: Academic and higher education staff.

Aims:

- Sharing information on RIRs at the partner institutions.
- Giving access to scientists from partner universities.
- Connect the academic community and facilitate interdisciplinary research cooperation.

Features needed:

- Searching tools for connected RIRs and harvesting data from existing catalogues on RIRs at the partner institutions.
- Sharing of instructive webinars on how to use RIRs.
- Information on events, projects, networking opportunities, and funding opportunities for

the RIRs.

- Storage of relevant documents, papers and books regarding the RIRs.
- Matchmaking between RIRs (see above).
- Presentation of best practices to the interested public.
- Newsletter on recently added RIR, upcoming webinars, etc.
- Entry point to the RIR.

Who should maintain/operate:

- Research professionals at each university.
- IT professionals.

Strategic goals addressed:

- Establishing Interdisciplinary Hubs.
- Training Researchers of the Future.
- Strengthening Collaboration Beyond Academia.
- Supporting Bottom-Up Initiatives.
- Promoting Mobility and Community Building.
- Digitalising Collaboration.
- Strengthening Research and Data Infrastructure Skills.

Existing commercial products: Hevo Data, GigaSpaces, Airbyte, Snowflake's Unistore, Stitch.

Short, middle and long-term goals:

The first short-term goal would be to establish an Una Europa digital catalogue (operational data store) of the RIR by harvesting data from the existing sources, including setting up a searching tool. The dedicated Una Europa platform could then successively add information on events, projects, networking, and funding opportunities related to the RIR. In the medium term, the collaboration requires data infrastructures. The long-term perspective is for the platform to be the central place for accessing the shared RIRs in Una Europa. Funding opportunities at the European level would be useful to develop data sharing tools and identify legal barriers. A matchmaking between RIRs could be part of a broader matchmaking page for Una Europa researchers, where they can express interest and needs and post information and opportunities. Ideally, Una Europa should develop a systematic way to link the infrastructures to research funding matchmaking.

Enhancing citizen science in research

Target group: Academics, higher education staff, citizens.

Aim:

- Presentation and communication of research projects to the general public.
- Project incubator as an open forum to suggest projects and engage with citizens.
- Matchmaking between researchers for joint citizen science projects.
- Matchmaking between researchers and/or research support staff for exchanging experience and best practice.

Features needed:

- Presentation of citizen engagement projects.
- Portal for matchmaking and expression of interest for joint projects.
- Online training.
- Storage of workshop recordings.

Who should maintain/operate:

- Research professionals at each university for specified research areas.
- IT professionals.

Strategic goals addressed:

- Establishing Interdisciplinary Hubs.
- Training Researchers of the Future.
- Strengthening Collaboration Beyond Academia.
- Supporting Bottom-Up Initiatives.
- Promoting Mobility and Community Building.
- Digitalising Collaboration.
- Promoting openness of RIs and data infrastructures to foster research collaboration.
- Strengthening Research and Data Infrastructure Skills.
- Developing a stronger and more integrated Una Europa Research Infrastructure Ecosystem.

Existing commercial products: See above.

Short, middle and long-term goals:

The first step to allow for a more concentrated approach would be to establish easy and efficient ways of communication and matchmaking between Una Europa researchers interested in citizen science, as well as between researchers and citizens. To this end, links to existing data bases with citizen science projects at individual universities could be gathered on the Una Europa Platform. In the medium term, a search for researchers doing projects on citizen science, or researchers interested in them should be possible on the Una Europa research information system via a label or hashtag system that could be added to researchers/projects profile. A search engine should be able to provide a specific search for such labels/hashtags. Similarly, the Una Europa platform dedicated to research funding opportunities should contain information on calls relevant to citizen science, which will require developing an associated filter. Alternatively, citizen science projects can have a separate page and be curated by research teams.

Sustainability of the pilot project

In the short term, the sustainability of the project may be best achieved by adapting commercial platforms, as developing a platform with all the desired functionality will require a highly complex digital architecture. There are skills and knowledge on harvesting data within our partner universities, e.g., at KU Leuven and at the University of Edinburgh, and Una Europa should take advantage of these existing skills.

Una.Resin WP1 has been in contact with Una Europa vzw about the pilot findings, which will feed into the process of designing an Una.Connect collaborative platform. Although a preliminary mapping of commercial platforms has already revealed some potential costs, there is need to carry out a cost analysis to inform the next stage of activity and to determine the value of further work. A considerable amount of additional funding will undoubtedly be required to develop a holistic, Alliance-wide platform that satisfies the needs of project management, communication within the Alliance, data storage, and the specific desires identified by researchers in this pilot.

Lessons learnt

Considerable resource is required to conceive, develop, and implement a collaborative

platform and, due to not having the financial or human resource required, the development and testing of tools at a large scale could not be carried out. However, a number of important lessons were still learnt. The most important outcome from the stakeholder consultations was that the platform should be simple, intuitive, and easy to use. All given information needs to be visible and transparent. For a collaborative platform to be an efficient tool for researchers and external partners, it needs to facilitate their work and not add more complexity to their daily tasks. This is a challenge for an Alliance that has a number of different projects, each with their own tasks, functions, and rationale. Even if Una Europa aimed not to use just one platform but to collect features from different sources, every aspect has to be clearly communicated on the Una Europa website to guarantee easy access and to avoid the current situation where multiple landing pages and platforms are simultaneously in use at the same time.

Recommendations for the future

To ensure that the needs of the researchers are heard, Una.Resin is working closely with Una Europa vzw to make sure that the insights from this pilot are used in the process of conceptualising a broader Una Europa platform. WP1 members have participated in the stakeholder consultations for the design of the Una.Connect platform, where preliminary results of this mapping have already been discussed. WP1 will continue to provide feedback on the proposed platform. This pilot evaluation will also be used in the process of developing the Una.Connnet platform and to give direction to future research collaborations within Una Europa, but also possibly within other university consortia of similar size and aspiration. For a platform to function in the long run, it would be necessary to guarantee ample funding for the findings to be put to use.